

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**THE EFFECTS OF URBANISATION ON GENERAL
ENVIRONMENT AND THE EFFECTIVENESS OF
PLANTATION IN INCREASING HEALTH EXPECTANCIES**

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Article Received: October 2019 **Accepted:** November 2019 **Published:** December 2019

Abstract:

Objective: The research objective is to determine the effects of geographical degradation and environmental hazards on public health.

Methods: The research type is ecological, that we conducted at Sir Ganga Ram Hospital, Lahore from August 2018 to January 2019. We took a sample from both developing and developed countries taking health profiles like health expenses, life expectancy, urbanization, geographical profile of agricultural land and forests, and environmental profile of noise-pollution index, and air. We analysed data through MS-Excel.

Results: We took twenty countries with 20% (4) and 80% (16) of developed and developing respectively. The number of developed and developing countries was 40% (4) and 80% (16) respectively out of twenty. Less polluted countries were 25% (5) which were modestly forested and 35% (7) were polluted. Agrarian states were 44% (7) having developed 50% (2) and developing 31% (5) having correlation sustenance with proportion to prolonged, healthy life-expectancy. The number of countries validated healthy life-expectancy with health expenditures and urbanisation was 75% (15) with the exception of 31% (5) countries developing and 70% (14) respectively.

Conclusion: Our ecological resources are facing great threats from an increase in urbanisation and plantation is one of the effective remedies for it.

Keywords: Environmental hazards, Plantation, Geographical degradation, Health expenditure, and Particulate Matter (PM).

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Please cite this article in press Rana Shahzad Murtaza et al., *The Effects Of Urbanisation On General Environment And The Effectiveness Of Plantation In Increasing Health Expectancies.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2019; 06(12).

INTRODUCTION:

The only known existed place for life is earth having $\frac{3}{4}$ part of water with $\frac{1}{4}$ part of the land, inhabiting millions of species and their life-mechanism. Plants being the oldest species, provide food, fuel, clothes, shelter, oxygen, and medicine to all on earth and in water, fulfilling most of the needs [1]. The world has become a better place due to globalization, economic progression, technological advancements and nuclear developments but this has caused serious health issues. The increase in urbanization led us to environmental hazards, endangering flora and fauna and decreasing health status [2]. The purpose of our study is to highlight how geographical degradation and environmental hazards effect on health status.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

The research type is ecological, that we conducted at Sir Ganga Ram Hospital, Lahore from August 2018 to January 2019. We included data from both developing and developed countries related to proportionate quota-sampling. We took the figurative data from WHO (World Health Organisation), WHR (World Health Rankings), United Nations, World Bank, and ISNM (International Statistics at Nation Master) [3, 5, 6, 4, 7]. Among developing countries, we selected Central Africa, Brunei, Ghana, China, Kenya, Oman, Madagascar, Qatar, Sierra Leone, Russia, South Africa, Singapore, Uruguay, Suriname, Timor-Leste, and Tuvalu. Among the developed countries, we selected Japan, Canada, Switzerland, and Australia

[6]. We preferred the countries where access and availability to data were easier with existence of our considered variables. We analyzed parameters related to health profiles like health expenses, life expectancy, urbanization, geographical profile of agricultural land and forests, and environmental profile of noise-pollution index, and air. We determined mean for each variable and analyzed values in accordance with relevant organization's set acceptable figures for each variable. We coded these values as above, around, and below acceptable figures with high, moderate, and low key-term respectively. We assumed plantation level as requirement of oxygen-per-individual equals to 7 tresses, and a large plant/Sq. feet or (83441 plants/Sq. Km) [8, 9]. Correlation analysis was the basis for interferences and contrasting variables. We used MS-Excel to analyse data.

RESULT:

We took twenty countries with 20% (4) and 80% (16) of developed and developing respectively. The number of developed and developing countries was 40% (4) and 80% (16) respectively out of twenty. Less polluted countries were 25% (5) which were modestly forested and 35% (7) were polluted. Agrarian stated were 44% (7) having developed 50% (2) and developing 31% (5) having correlation sustenance with proportion to prolonged, healthy life-expectancy. The number of countries validated healthy life-expectancy with health expenditures and urbanisation was 75% (15) with the exception of 31% (5) countries developing and 70% (14) respectively.

Table – I: Health Profile, Geographical Area and Environmental Profile

Countries		Switzerland	Japan	Canada	Australia	Mean	
Health Profile	Healthy Life Expectancy	73.1	74.9	72	71.9	73	
	GDP%	11.7	10.2	10.4	9.4	10	
	Per Capita	9674	3703	5292	6031	6175	
Geographical Profile	Urban Area	%	20	30	1	0	13
		Per Capita	0.1	0.09	0.36	0.16	0.17
	Forest Area	%	32	69	38	16	39
		Per Capita	0.15	0.2	9.81	5.43	4
	Agricultural Area	%	39	12	7	53	28
		Per Capita	0.05	0.03	1.29	2	1
Environmental Profile	Air Pollution PM 2.5	13	13	7	6	10	
	Light & Noise Pollution	42.86	45	40.11	25.74	38	

Table – II: Developed Versus Developing Countries

Countries	Population (X1)	Land area Trees Requisition by Plant			
		sq.km (X2)	Population (100,000) Requisition B	Land Area (100,000)	
Developed Countries	Australia	22992654	7682300	1609	6410188
	Canada	35362905	9093510	2475	7587716
	Japan	126702133	364560	8869	304193
	Switzerland	8179294	39516	573	32973
Developing Countries	Brunei	436620	5270	31	4397
	Cent. Africa	5507257	622980	386	519821
	China	1373541278	9388211	96148	7833617
	Ghana	26908262	227540	1884	189862
	Kenya	47615739	569140	3333	474896
	Madagascar	24430325	581800	1710	485460
	Oman	3424386	309500	240	258250
Qatar	2258283	11610	158	9688	

DISCUSSION:

The estimation of mean urbanisation is 5% among high-income, 2% among middle and 0.2% among low-income countries [4]. European states have (2-8%) range [10]. Singapore and Tuvalu have the most and the least urbanisation respectively [4]. Increase in urbanisation is a great threat to global environmental resources. By 2030, 60% population may have switched to urban from rural [2]. This may decrease flora and fauna, increase environmental hazards, and decrease health status. Worldwide, 14% and 28% of developed and developing countries respectively have a large infertile and meagrely vegetated land [11]. There have been 2.7 million deaths due to insufficient food/vegetable intake [12]. The most hazardous to human health currently is air pollution. A WHO report mentions 7 million mortalities globally due to inhalation of adulterated air. There have been 2.6 million mortalities caused by outdoor air-pollution and 3.3 million by indoor air pollution with the rate of 12% and 88% among developed and developing countries respectively. The most concentrated areas are South East Asia and Western Pacific [13]. Worldwide, the outdoor and indoor air pollution has caused COPD (Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease) among children with the rate of 11% and 22%, lower respiratory infection (acute) with 3% and 12%, ischaemic heart disease with 40% and 26%, lung cancer with 6% both, and stroke with 40% and 34% respectively [3]. Studies observe a Particulate Matter of 2.5 of air pollution among developed countries between (13-18 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) mean each year. This rate is lower than developing countries. WHO has set standard of air quality of PM 2.5 (10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) as preferable, (11-19.40 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) as acceptable, and beyond 15 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ is considered hazardous for health [14]. The

infertile, barren land of Oman and Qatar stands at the highest pollution index [4]. Countries having pollution index significantly higher like Ghana, Central Africa, Madagascar, Kenya, South Africa, and Sierra Leone has least life-expectancies [4, 5]. Human activities cause nine billion tons of emission of carbon-dioxide, ending up four into atmosphere, 3 terrestrial and 2 billion tons into aquatic [5].

Industrial, locomotive and domestic activities daily emit carbon monoxide, ozone, lead, sulphur dioxide, nitrogen dioxide, and particulates into the atmosphere and jeopardizes human health [16]. These activities create noise pollution making repugnant distractions for human ears. The damage of these polluted activities goes beyond auditory, damaging heart, brain, liver, kidneys, cardiovascular, respiratory, neurological, and digestive systems [17]. Unplanned, congested buildings, cables, billboards etc. hinder an individual's peace blocking nature from his sight [18]. The perception index of pollution on intense light and noise is higher among developing countries than developed countries [7]. It was highest in Sierra Leone and Ghana and lowest in Brunei and Australia [7]. Plantation boosts health effectively. An estimation shows that a human inhales 9.5 tonnes of air/year (740kg oxygen/year) with each breath of 1/3, which is worth (7-8) trees [8]. Forests cover earth's 30%, are the largest providers of carbon dioxide (45%) and plants' yield (50%) [4, 15]. A desirable forestation level is (25-50%) for any country with industrial/agricultural needs [19]. Land with trees eradicates carbon, particulates, nitrogen dioxide, sulphur dioxide, and carbon monoxide daily with a rate of 100 Lbs., 48 Lbs., 9 Lbs., 6 Lbs., and 0.5 Lbs. respectively [20]. Japan, Canada, Switzerland, and

Brunei have dense forests and celebrates pollution-free environment with prolonged life-expectancy [4, 5]. A land of (0.1 ha/person) cultivated and arable provides sustainability to an individual [11]. We found a (0.2-to-0.7 ha/capita) estimation of cultivation land in developed countries while (0.2 ha/capita) in the developing countries [11]. We also observed actual utilisation of the agriculture land in developed countries to be 52.9% and 7.2% in Australia and Canada (sustenance of 2.00 and 1.29 ha/capita) respectively and in developing countries to be (54.8%, 13.2%, 0.5%, 25.6%, and 82.1%) in China, Russia, Suriname, Timor-Leste, and Uruguay (sustenance of 0.08, 0.8, 0.1, 0.1, and 0.7 ha/capita) respectively [4]. According to a study a 129 Sq. Ft plant improves health [9]. Dense greenery and vegetation increases mental health and provides a healthy lifestyle. A decreased greenery in the neighbourhood leads to poor health and does not soothe mind [21]. Indoor greenery oxygenates the air, makes it cool, toxin-free and hygienic which nourishes mental and physical health [9]. Indoor plants aid in health improvement by providing an ambience with less oxygen after sunset [22]. Plants also provide relief to physical and mental illness. Plants increase proficiency and productivity, accelerate recovery after surgery, and bring physiological regulation in body [23]. Plants intensify memory, creativity and productivity by (20%, 45%, and 38%) respectively also provides defence against frequently recurring issue like dry throat, runny nose, coughing, eye itching, illness, and fatigue by (20%, 20%, 35%, 20%, 20%, and 30%) respectively [13]. Consuming fruits, vegetables help in cure, provide defence against chronic conditions, prevents diseases, and provide side-effects free remedies [12]. WHO prefers 5% of GDP (Gross Domestic Product) allocation for health expenses or (\$44/capita) is an alternative recommendation [24, 25]. Health expenditures are different for varying regions. We can assess health outlays through healthy life-expectancy of a region. It is not sure that a country spending a lot on health should enjoy the most prolonged, healthy life. Health expense of Switzerland is \$9674/capita with 62% health while Japan has longer healthy life with \$3703/capita expense. Same goes for Timor-Leste (\$57/capita), China (\$420/capita), Suriname (\$589/capita), Oman (\$675/capita), Russia (\$893/capita), and Brunei (\$958 /capita), having longer life expectancies [4, 5]. Tuvalu, South Africa, Sierra Leone, Kenya, and Ghana spend (\$633, \$570, \$86, \$78, and \$58) respectively and spend shortened life-span [4, 5]. An estimation shows (3-4) months increase in life-expectancy with a 10% increase in health-outlays [24, 26]. With the limitation of time and unavailability of data, we selected countries having

easy access and rich trends. However, further studies should conduct more and more countries around the globe.

CONCLUSION:

The increase in urbanisation is a serious ecological threat, endangering natural resources including flora and fauna, decreasing health parameters. Plantation is an effective way of reducing pollution and enhancing health expectancy.

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